

AVAILABILITY AND UTILIZATION OF AI-ENHANCED ASSISTIVE DEVICES AMONG STUDENTS WITH EMOTIONAL AND BEHAVIOURAL DISORDERS: IMPLICATIONS FOR REHABILITATION PRACTICES

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Abstract

AI-enhanced assistive devices are transforming the way students with emotional and behavioural disorders (EBD) learn and interact. The study investigated the availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with Emotional and Behavioural Disorders (EBD) at the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. The study adopted a descriptive research design. Two research questions and one hypothesis were used to guide the study. Literature review was conducted according to the variables of the study. The purposive sampling technique was used to select 60 respondents for the study. A checklist and a questionnaire were used for data collection. Simple percentage and Pearson-Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) were employed for data analysis. Findings revealed that a good number of personal AI-enhanced assistive devices were available among students with Emotional and Behavioural Disorders in FCE(S), Oyo. Students with Emotional and Behavioural Disorders in FCE(S), Oyo utilize AI-enhanced assistive devices on a personal basis to improve their academic skills. It was revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization and academic skills of students with Emotional and Behavioural Disorders in FCE(S), Oyo ($r_{cal} = 0.645, p < 0.05$). It was concluded that AI-enhanced assistive devices are available and utilized for academic skills development among students with Emotional and Behavioural Disorders in FCE(S), Oyo. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the educational policy-makers, school administrators, teachers, parents and educational rehabilitation centers should encourage the use of AI-enhanced assistive devices to improve the academic skills of students with Emotional and Behavioural Disorders. Implications for rehabilitation practices were discussed.

Key Words: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Emotional and Behavioral Disorders (EBD), Academic Skills, Educational Rehabilitation, Inclusion.

Introduction

Students with emotional and behavioural disorders often face significant challenges in an academic setting, impacting their learning outcomes and social interactions, which necessitate the need for rehabilitation services. Assistive technology, including AI-enhanced devices, can potentially mitigate these challenges by providing personalized support, improving accessibility, and enhancing engagement.

Emotional and behavioral disorders (EBD) refer to a spectrum of psychological conditions affecting students' behavior, emotions, and moods (Ameesi & Yellowe, 2018). It is a behavior disorder or mental illness characterized by: the inability to learn which cannot be explained by intellectual, cultural, sensory or health factors; an inability to build or maintain satisfactory interrelationships with peers and teachers; inappropriate types of behavior or feelings under normal circumstances; a general pervasive mood of unhappiness or depression; a tendency to develop physical symptoms of fears associated with personal or school problems (IDEA, 2004). According to Jackson (2021), students with emotional and behavioural disorders (EBD) often display a range of challenging behaviors, such as: aggression – verbal or physical aggression towards others, such as hitting, pushing, or yelling; hyperactivity – excessive restlessness, impulsivity, or difficulty remaining seated or focused; learning difficulties – struggles with academic tasks, such as completing assignments or following instructions; child-like emotions – inappropriate emotional responses, such as tantrums or excessive emotional reactivity; and withdrawal – social withdrawal, isolation, or difficulty interacting with peers or adults. These behaviours can vary in severity and impact students' academic, social, and emotional competency. Understanding the complexities of emotional and behavioural disorders is crucial for the development of supportive devices and interventions (Kundu et al, 2023). Such supportive devices include AI-enhanced assistive devices for students with emotional and behavioural disorders (EBD).

The provision of AI-enhanced assistive devices is an effective strategy for equalizing educational opportunities for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in an inclusive learning environment. It ensures access to education and guarantees equal academic performance for all. For learners with emotional and behavioural disorders, equal opportunity for academic performance has implications on teaching methodologies, instructional media, learning environment, classroom management and handling of examinations (Masayi, 2020).

According to the National Institute on Deafness and Other Communication Disorders (NIDCD, 2021), assistive devices could be defined as any item, piece of equipment, or product system, whether purchased commercially, modified, or customized, that is used to increase, maintain, or improve the functional capabilities of individuals with disabilities, especially students with emotional and behavioural disorders. Assistive devices provisions are services that directly help a person with a disability to choose, acquire, or utilize assistive devices equipment (NIDCD, 2021).

Numerous technologies assist students with emotional and behavioural disorders. The same is broadly classified into three: assistive devices, augmentative and alternative assistive devices and alerting assistive devices (McNicholl et al., 2021). The choice of one assistive device over

another is dependent on specific needs or attributes, and it may change over time or in different situations. Wein (2014) argued that assistive devices give students with emotional and behavioural disorders the independence to execute things that they formerly had difficulty with or were unable to complete, by providing enhanced abilities through assistive devices. They offer alternative ways of accomplishing tasks, actions, and activities, as well as assisting students with disabilities in reaching their full potential, such as achieving educational goals (McNicholl et al., 2021).

The Nigerian government has stated through its educational laws and policies that learners with disabilities shall be provided with the necessary facilities, equipment, materials, and other assistive devices to ensure easy access to quality education for learners with special needs in inclusive schools (FRN, 2023). Section 18 (1b) of the Disability Act, 2018 specifically stated that all public schools, whether primary, secondary, or tertiary shall be run to be inclusive of and accessible to persons with disabilities; accordingly, every school shall have special facilities for the effective education of persons with disabilities (Bamisaye, 2024). Specifically, the education of students with emotional and behavioural disorders could be facilitated by the incorporation of AI-enhanced assistive devices (Sambu et al., 2018).

AI-enhanced assistive devices are tools that utilize artificial intelligence (AI) to provide support and assistance to individuals with disabilities, including students with emotional and behavioural disorders (Koweru et al 2015). These devices can help improve daily life, increase adaptability, help in emotional adjustment, and behaviour modification among students with emotional and behaviour disorders. The benefits of AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization among students with emotional and behavioural disorders cannot be overemphasized (Kundu et al 2020). It provides personalized support, improve accessibility, and enhance engagement, among other benefits. Examples of AI-enhanced assistive devices include: Speech-to-Text System – which can transcribe spoken language into written text, helping students with emotional and behavioural disorders to manage and regulate their emotions by expressing themselves using alternative means of communication; Text-to-Speech System – which can convert written text into spoken language, assisting students with emotional and behavioural disorders to express their feelings without throwing tantrum or displaying behaviour disorders; Virtual Assistance – This includes Google Assistance which can perform tasks, provide information, and offer support to students with emotional and behavioural disorders; Wearable Devices – Such as smartwatches or fitness trackers that helps monitor health metrics, track activities, regulate emotions and provide alerts for students with emotional and behavioural disorders; and Communication Devices – AI-enhanced communication devices, such as picture communication symbols or augmentative and alternative communication (AAC) devices, can help students with emotional and behavioural disorders to express themselves more effectively (Ngonyani & Mnyanyi, 2021).

Literature reveals that there were few studies conducted on the availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders. Most studies have focused on the challenges, factors and causes of poor academic performance and poor communication issues rather than on AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with disabilities (Onivehu et al 2017). Specifically, the availability and utilization of AI-enhanced

assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders is yet to be investigated. Therefore, this study found a landing ground to bridge the gap by investigating the availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.

Statement of the Problem

Students with emotional and behavioural disorders (EBD) often experience significant challenges in emotional regulation, behaviour, and communication skills. Consequently, these challenges can impact their academic performance, social interactions, emotional skills, and mental well-being. It is observed by the researchers that the rate of school dropout, unplanned pregnancy, emotional distress and poor academic performance is becoming high among students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. However, AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization might help in providing solutions to these challenges.

Various studies have primarily focused on students with emotional and behavioural disorders and assistive devices. However, no study had been conducted on the availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. This indicated a gap left behind by the previous researchers in the literature, which necessitate the conduct of this study. Therefore, the present study aimed at investigating the availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. Specific purposes are:

1. To investigate the availability of AI-enhanced assistive devices for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.
2. To investigate the level of AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization by students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.
3. To investigate the impact of AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization on the rehabilitation programme for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. Are AI-enhanced assistive devices available for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo?
2. What is the level of AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization by students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo?

Hypothesis

This hypothesis was formulated to guide the study and be tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀ There is no significant relationship between AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization and rehabilitation programme for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.

Methodology

A mixed-methods design incorporating both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection and analysis was adopted for this study. The population for the study consist of 65 students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. The purposive sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 60 respondents. The remaining five members of the population did not consent to participate in the study due to their tight lecture schedule. The urposive sampling technique was used since the respondents must meet certain conditions, which include being identified as students with emotional and behavioural disorders (Umoru, 2022). The instruments used for data collection include a questionnaire for quantitative data collection and a structured interview for qualitative data collection. The content validity of which was achieved by submitting the instruments to two other professional colleagues in the Department of Communication and Behavioural Disorders and the Department of Rehabilitation Education in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, for scrutiny. The reliability of the instruments was obtained using a trial-test method in a pilot school different from the locale of the study. The questionnaire was graded to four-likert scale point with Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The questionnaire was administered on respondents who volunteered to participate and signed the consent form, while a high level of confidentiality was maintained. Descriptive methods of data analysis and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) were used to analyze. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for data analysis.

Result

RQ 1: Are AI-enhanced assistive devices available for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo?

Table 1: Percentage and mean scores showing the availability of AI-enhanced assistive devices for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN
1.	AI-enhanced assistive devices are available in our school	2 (3.3%)	14(23.3%)	32 (53.3%)	12 (20%)	2.1
2.	Our school have enough AI-enhanced assistive devices	-	9 (15%)	33(55%)	18 (30%)	1.9
3.	Our school have variety of AI-enhanced assistive devices	3 (5%)	7 (11.7%)	28(46.7%)	22(36.7%)	1.9
4.	AI-enhanced assistive devices are easily accessible in our school	-	-	34(56.7%)	26(43.3%)	1.6
5.	Learners are allowed to bring AI-enhanced assistive devices into the classroom	5 (5%)	8 (13.3%)	34(56.7%)	15 (25%)	2.1
6.	Our school has clear instructions on how to access AI-enhanced assistive devices	-	12 (20%)	35(58.3%)	17(28.3%)	2.1
7.	Learners utilizing the AI-enhanced assistive devices are recognized at our school	-	10 (16.7%)	28(46.7%)	22(36.7%)	1.8
8.	The AI-enhanced assistive devices are repaired in timely manner	-	9 (15%)	28(46.7%)	23(38.3%)	1.8
	Weighted Average					1.91

Table 1 reveals that students with emotional and behavioural disorders disagreed that AI-enhanced assistive devices are available in their schools (2.1). They also disagreed that their school have enough AI-enhanced assistive devices (1.9). They disagreed that their schools have a variety of AI-enhanced assistive devices (1.9). They disagreed that AI-enhanced assistive devices are easily accessible in their schools (1.6). They disagreed that learners are allowed to bring AI-enhanced assistive devices into the classroom (2.1). Also, the learners disagreed that their schools had clear instructions on how to access AI-enhanced assistive devices (2.1). They disagreed that learners utilizing the AI-enhanced assistive devices are recognized at their school (1.8). They disagreed that AI-enhanced assistive devices are repaired in timely manner (1.8). The overall weighted average mean was 1.91, which indicated that the calculated mean (1.91) is less than the fixed mean (2.50). This implied that AI-enhanced assistive devices for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, were grossly unavailable, limited or hard to find in schools.

RQ 2: What is the level of AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization by students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo?

Table 2: Percentage scores showing the level of AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization by students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo

S/N	Item	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN
1	I often use AI-enhanced assistive devices as part of my rehabilitation program.	2 (3.3%)	14(23.3%)	32 (53.3%)	12 (20%)	2.1
2	I often use emotional regulation and self-monitoring apps to manage my emotions.	-	9 (15%)	33(55%)	18 (30%)	1.9
3	I often use text-to-speech apps as alternative means of expressing my feeling.	3 (5%)	7 (11.7%)	28(46.7%)	22(36.7%)	1.9
4	I often use wearable devices to monitor my emotions and give me alerts.	-	-	34(56.7%)	26(43.3%)	1.6
5	I use AI-enhanced assistive devices to reduce stress and anxiety regularly.	5 (5%)	8 (13.3%)	34(56.7%)	15 (25%)	2.1
6	I use AI-enhanced assistive devices to improve my communication skills regularly.	-	12 (20%)	35(58.3%)	17(28.3%)	2.1
7	I use AI-enhanced assistive devices to improve my academic performance regularly.	-	10 (16.7%)	28(46.7%)	22(36.7%)	1.8
8	The use of AI-enhanced assistive devices has positively impacted my rehabilitation progress.	-	9 (15%)	28(46.7%)	23(38.3%)	1.8
	Weighted Average					1.91

Table 2 reveals that students with emotional and behavioural disorders disagreed that they often use AI-enhanced assistive devices as part of their rehabilitation program (2.1). They also disagreed that they often use emotional regulation and self-monitoring apps to manage their emotions (1.9). They disagreed that they often use text-to-speech apps as alternative means of expressing their feelings (1.9). Furthermore, they disagreed that they often use wearable devices to monitor their emotions and give them alerts (1.6). They also disagreed that they use AI-enhanced assistive devices to reduce stress and anxiety regularly (2.1). They disagreed that they use AI-enhanced assistive devices to improve their communication skills regularly (2.1). They also disagreed that they used AI-enhanced assistive devices to improve their academic performance regularly (1.8). More so, they disagreed that their use of AI-enhanced assistive devices has positively impacted their rehabilitation progress (1.8). The overall weighted average mean was 1.91, which indicated that the calculated mean (1.9) is less than the fixed mean (2.5). This implies that the level of AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization by students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo was low.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization and rehabilitation programme for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo.

Table 3: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) showing the significant relationship between AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization and rehabilitation programme for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo

Variables	N	MEAN	SD	r-cal	Df	p-value	DECISION
AI-enhanced Assistive Devices Utilization	60	26.35	5.69	0.645	53	0.001	Sig
Rehabilitation Program	60	23.29	4.46				

Table 3 shows the relationship between AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization and rehabilitation programme for students with emotional and behavioural disorders. It was revealed that the mean and standard deviation of AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization were 26.35 and 5.69, respectively, while the mean and standard deviation of the rehabilitation programme were 23.29 and 4.46, respectively. The calculated value of r_{cal} was 0.645, and the degree of freedom was 53; the observed p-value was 0.001 and the fixed p-value was 0.05. The observed p-value was less than the fixed p-value ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization and rehabilitation programme for students with emotional and behavioural disorders was not accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization and rehabilitation programme for students with emotional and behavioural disorders.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study revealed that a good number of AI-enhanced assistive devices are not adequately available for students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, except for a few apps on their personal mobile phones. Since the devices are not adequately available, it becomes difficult for the students to enhance their rehabilitation and academic progress. This could be a result of the high cost of the devices. Olugu (2020) affirmed that the poor availability of assistive devices is because of the expensive nature of the devices for students with emotional and behavioural disorders, as well as a few availability of assistive devices for students. This finding is in line with Anyaoha et al. (2022) who discovered that assistive devices are grossly inadequate in Nigeria's special educational institutions.

The inadequate availability of AI-enhanced assistive devices also affected their utilization among students with emotional and behavioural disorders in the Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo. This finding corroborated the findings of Ebuenyi et al. (2023), who reported that assistive device utilization by students was poor in South-East Nigeria. Students with emotional and behavioural disorders should be provided with AI-enhanced assistive devices in order to encourage their utilization and thereby improve their rehabilitation and academic progress.

The result of the hypothesis revealed that there is a significant relationship between AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization and rehabilitation programme for students with emotional and behavioural disorders. AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization is pertinent for improving emotional and behavioural skills of students with emotional and behavioural disorders. The availability and accessibility of AI-enhanced assistive devices determine their utilization and consequential benefits attached to it. The findings agreed with Soetan et al. (2021) who discovered that before assistive devices are utilized, they must be readily available and accessible to learners, and teachers or learners must be trained to acquire operational competence, functional competence, strategic competence and social competence of all the AI-enhanced assistive devices.

Implications for Rehabilitation Practices

The integration of AI-enhanced assistive devices in rehabilitation practices for students with emotional and behavioural disorders has transformative potential. These devices can provide personalized support, improve accessibility, and enhance engagement, ultimately leading to better learning outcomes and emotional stability. The availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders have positive implications for rehabilitation practices as they empower students to take greater control of their emotional and behavioural well-being. It also provides educators and therapists with valuable data on students' rehabilitation progress, enabling them to refine intervention strategies. The availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders can facilitate more effective collaboration between students, educators, and therapists, promoting better support and understanding.

Conclusion

The study on the availability and utilization of AI-enhanced assistive devices among students with emotional and behavioural disorders in Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, reveals a concerning gap between the potential benefits of these devices and their current availability and utilization. Despite the potential of AI-enhanced assistive devices to support rehabilitation practices, the study finds that these devices are inadequately available in the college, and their utilization among the students is low. This situation underscores the need for concerted efforts to bridge this gap and harness the benefits of AI-enhanced assistive devices for students with emotional and behavioural disorders.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. The school administrators should increase the availability of AI-enhanced assistive devices, train both educators and therapists on the use of the devices, support and create awareness of AI-enhanced assistive devices in the college community.

- ii. Educators and rehabilitation therapists should incorporate AI-enhanced assistive devices into individualized rehabilitation plans, personalize their support and monitor student progress for improvement among students with emotional and behavioural disorders.
- iii. Policymakers should allocate sufficient funds to support the acquisition and maintenance of AI-enhanced assistive devices, develop and implement policies that promote the use of AI-enhanced assistive devices, and foster collaborations between educational institutions, technology developers, and relevant stakeholders to ensure the development of AI-enhanced assistive devices that meet the needs of students with emotional and behavioural disorders.

References

- Amesi, A., & Yellowe, I. T. (2018). Availability and utilization of information and communication technology gadgets in faculties of education in Rivers State Universities, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 4(4), 26-36.
- Anyaocha, A. C., Bosah, I. P., & Oluwatayo, J. C. (2022). Availability of assistive technologies for teaching pupils with learning disabilities in special education centres in Anambra State. *South Eastern Journal of Research and Sustainable Development*. 9(1):18-36
- Bamisaye, M. O. (2024). Teachers' awareness, knowledge and implementation of the Disability Act, 2018 in public secondary schools in Kwara State. [Masters Thesis, Kwara State University], Nigeria. Available at <https://www.proquest.com/openview>
- Ebuenyi, I. D., Kafumba, J., Smith, E. M, Jamali-Phiri, M. Z, Munthali, A, MacLachlan, M. (2023). Empirical research and available data on assistive technology for persons with disabilities in Malawi: A review. *Assist. Technol* 35(1):94-106
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2023). *Nigerian National Policy on Inclusive Education. (Revised Edition)*. NERDC Press
- Johnson, E. (2021). *Disability, stigma and assistive devices*. Retrieved on 15th June, 2025, from <https://www.leonardcheshire.org>
- Koweru, R. A., Omoke, C. M., & Orodho, J. A. (2015). The role of assistive devices on quality educational outcomes of students with visual impairment in Kisumu County, Kenya. *IOSR Journal of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 20(3), 39-50.
- Kundu, A., Bej, T., & Dey, K. N. (2020). Indian educators' awareness and attitude towards assistive devices. *Journal of Enabling Technologies*, 14(4), 233-251.
- Masayi, D. (2020). *Relationship between utilization of assistive hearing technology and academic performance of learners in schools for the deaf in Kakamega County, Kenya*. [Masters thesis, Kenyatta University]. Kenya.

- McNicholl, A., Casey, H., Desmond, D., & Gallagher, P. (2021). The impact of assistive devices use for learners with disabilities in higher education: a systematic review. *Disability and Rehabilitation: Assistive Devices*, 16(2), 130-143.
- National Institute on Deafness and Other Communication Disorders (2021). *Assistive devices for People with Hearing, Voice, Speech, or Language Disorders*. Retrieved on 15th June, 2025 from <https://www.nidcd.nih.gov/health/assistive-devices>
- Ngonyani, J. C., & Mnyanyi, C. B. (2021). Assessing the relevance of assistive devices for persons with disabilities in higher learning institutions: a case of University of Dar Es Salaam in Tanzania. *European Journal of Special Education Research*, 7 (2), 42-70.
- Olugu, F. (2020). Availability and utilization of assistive technology devices for improved teaching and learning among students with learning disabilities in Ohafia, Abia State. Retrieved on 4th September, 2024 from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3568523>.
- Onivehu, A. O., Ohawuiro, O. E., & Oyeniran, B. J. (2017). Teachers' attitude and competence in the use of assistive devices in Special Needs Schools. *Acta Didactica Napocensia*, 10 (4), 21-32.
- Sambu, M. C., Otube, N., & Bunyasi, B. A. (2018). Assessment of academic performance of students with emotional and behavioural disorders in selected special primary schools in Kenya. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 6 (2), 1-12.
- Soetan, A. K., Onojah, A. O., Alaka, T. B., & Onojah, A. A. (2021). Attitude of hearing impaired learners towards AI-enhanced assistive devices utilization in Oyo State, adopting the survey method. *Indonesian Journal of Community and Special Needs Education*, 1 (2), 103-118.
- Umoru, T. A. (2022). *Research Methods: fundamentals and application*. Academic Publishing Centre, North-East Zone.
- Wein, F. T. (2014). *Assistive devices Introduction*. Retrieved on 15th June, 2025 from <http://www.astericsacademy.net>